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ADJECTIVES IN TAMIL AND URDU – A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Dr. A. Mubarak Ali ^{*1}

^{*1} Annamalai University, INDIA

ABSTRACT

The aim of the paper is to compare the adjectives of Tamil Language which is one of the languages of Dravidian family and Urdu which is one of the members of Indo-Aryan family and bring out similarities and differences in their formation and usage in these two languages.

Keywords:

Adjectives, Simple adjectives, Derived Adjectives, adjectivalizer, Universal and specific.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Though the adjectives are universal to world languages, they differ in their function and occurrences. In some world languages the adjectives have to agree with the noun in respect of gender, number and definiteness and in respect of case endings and in other this is not the situation. In some world languages the adjectives are placed before the noun languages and the other placed after the noun and also the adjective is used with intensifier. Eventually this paper attempts to explain about the types and formation of adjectives in Tamil and Urdu Languages.

2. ADJECTIVES

Adjectives are words that describe or give information about nouns or pronouns. They are therefore often said to modify, or limit, nouns and pronouns. Adjectives are usually easy to recognize in a sentence, often describing or modifying an object's size colour or amount. (Pahuja.N.P:p5)

A word used with noun to describe or point out, the person, animal, place or thing which the noun names, or to tell the number or quantity, is called an Adjective. So we may define an Adjective as a word used with a noun to add something for its meaning (Wren & Marti:p-19)

	Tamil	Urdu
Person	nalla paiyan	acchaa ladkaa

	<i>Good boy</i> Nalla peN <i>Good girl</i>	<i>Good boy</i> <i>Acchi ladki</i> <i>Good girl</i>
Animal	Karuppu aaTu <i>Black goat</i> Uyarmaana aaTu <i>Tall goat</i>	kaalibakri <i>Black goat</i> Unci bakri <i>Tall goat</i>
Place	Periya kaTTiTam <i>Big building</i> Ciriya kaTTiTam <i>Small building</i>	badaa imaat <i>Big building</i> Chota imaat <i>Small building</i>

On the basis of their structure, the adjectives may be grouped into simple adjective and derived adjective.

SIMPLE ADJECTIVES

Those words which have adjectival function and which are not descriptively derived from any other grammatical derived from any other grammatical category are called simple adjective

Tamil	Urdu	Meaning
Nalla keTTa	achchaa qaraab	Good bad
Periya ciriya iniya	badaa choota MiiTha	Big small sweet

DERIVED ADJECTIVES

Givon (1970:816) remarked of English that “of all adjectives in the dictionary, only a small number are original or overtly underived; the great bulk are morphologically derived from either nouns or verbs, but there appear to be more derivations forming adjectives than for the other word classes. (Asher.R.E:p30)

Those words which have adjectival function and which are derived from nouns are called derived adjectives.

Tamil	Urdu	Meaning
Naankaavatu paTi	Chaarvisidi	fourth step
ALakaana pen	Khubsuurat ladki	beautiful girl
Viramulla paiyan	Baahadur ladkaa	bravest boy

arivuTaiya paiyan	Aql waalaa ladkaa	brilliant boy
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3. COMPARATIVE STUDY

Both in Tamil and Urdu, the adjectives are placed immediately before the noun. In Urdu, the simple adjectives are of two types, the first type adjectives shows agreement with the nouns according to gender and number which are qualified by adjectives as

kaalaa kapdaa (mas.sing)
Black cloth

kaali saadi (fem.sing)
Black saree

uncaa ladkaa
tall boy
unci ladki
tall girl

and the second type does not show any change as

laal kapdaa
Red cloth
laal saadi,
Red saree

Qaraab ladkaa
Bad boy
Qarab ladki
Bad girl

This situation does not prevail in Tamil

Karupput tuNi (neu.sing)
Black cloth
karuppup puTavai (neu.sing).
Black saree

keTTa paiyan
bad boy
keTTa peN
bad girl

uyarmaana paiyan
tall boy

uyarmaana peN
tall girl

For plural, the simple adjectives of Urdu show change according to number and gender as

kaale kapde (mas.pl.)
Black cloth
kaali sadiyan
Black sarees

But in Tamil this change is absent as

karupput tuNikaL (neu.pl.)
Black cloth
karuppup puTavaikaL
Black sarees

The derived adjectives in Urdu are formed with the adjectivalizer “waalaa”, “kaa” “vi” and in Tamil with “aana”, “uLLa” and “uTaiya” “aavatu”

Urdu	Tamil
gusse waalaa aadmi <i>The man with angry</i>	kopamaana manitan <i>The man with angry</i>
mohabbat waalaa aadmi <i>The man with affection</i>	anpaana manitan <i>The man with love</i>
kapdeekaa pardaa <i>Cloth curtain</i>	poruppuLLa manitan <i>The man with responsibility</i>
jhaadkaa palang <i>wooden cot</i>	PoruppuTaiya patavi <i>Responsible post</i>
chaarvi sidi <i>fourth step</i>	Naankavatu paTi <i>Fourth step</i>

4. CONCLUSION

In Urdu the simple adjectives are two types and in Tamil only one. The derived adjectives in Urdu are formed with the markers “waalaa” “kaa” “vi” and in Tamil with “aavatu” “aana”, “uLLa”, “uTaya”. In Urdu, the adjectives both simple and derived agree with the noun according to gender and number but the Tamil adjectives do not change. In Tamil and Urdu both simple and derived adjectives take a degree modifier as

Bahut acchaa ladkaa
Very good boy

migavum nalla paiyan
very good boy

This situation shows that the formation and function of adjectives are specific to languages of the world.

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